

The New Silk Road: Foreign Trade as an Inducer of National Development

*A Nova Rota da Seda:
Comércio Exterior Como Indutor do Desenvolvimento Nacional*
*La Nueva Ruta de la Seda:
El comercio exterior como inductor del desarrollo nacional*

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Abstract: This study focuses on contemporary Chinese foreign policy, particularly the development of the "New Silk Road" initiative. This ambitious project aims to connect the People's Republic of China (PRC) with Europe and Africa through a network of land and maritime routes, traversing key regions in Central Asia and the Middle East. The core objective of this research is to elucidate the terrestrial routes of this policy and the consequential influence of Chinese geopolitics in the international community, both currently and in the foreseeable future. The research approach employed is an integrative review, utilizing descriptive, qualitative, and exploratory case study methodologies. The study explores indications that China may not only integrate but also become a leading promoter of complete economic and commercial integration within the region and its vicinity. This is attributed to China's significant geopolitical role, its rapidly evolving market policies, and the immense growth potential, particularly in social and economic spheres. The analysis of these elements suggests a favorable scenario for China to implement its new initiative, potentially reshaping regional economic and geopolitical landscapes.

Keywords: *New Silk Road; China; Eurasia; Multipolar World.*

Resumo: A política externa chinesa na atualidade tem uma prioridade que é a construção de uma "Nova Rota da Seda", que ligará a RPC (República Popular da China) aos continentes europeu e africano por vias terrestres e marítimas, passando, conseqüentemente por países importantes da Ásia Central e do Oriente Médio. O objetivo deste estudo é apresentar as rotas terrestres relacionadas a essa política e a conseqüente relevância que a geopolítica chinesa exerce atualmente e passará a exercer nos próximos anos perante a comunidade internacional. A abordagem de pesquisa adotada para o desenvolvimento desse estudo é uma revisão integrativa, a partir da aplicação de uma metodologia de estudo do caso descritivo, qualitativo e exploratório. O presente estudo, busca indícios de que a China possa vir não só a integrar-se como também a ser a principal promotora das condições para a integração econômica e comercial plena de toda a região e adjacências, dado o destaque de seu papel geopolítico, e por contar com uma política de mercado em franco desenvolvimento e com grande potencial de crescimento, especialmente sob

as perspectivas sociais e econômicas. A análise desse conjunto de fatores sugere um cenário favorável para que a China coloque em prática a nova iniciativa.

Palavras-chave: Nova Rota da Seda; China; Eurásia; Mundo Multipolar.

Resumen: La política exterior china tiene hoy una prioridad, que es la construcción de una "Nueva Ruta de la Seda", que conectará la RPC (República Popular China) con los continentes europeo y africano por tierra y mar, pasando así por importantes países de Asia Central y Oriente Medio. El objetivo de este estudio es presentar ante la comunidad internacional las rutas terrestres relacionadas con esta política y la consecuente relevancia que la geopolítica china ejerce y ejercerá en los próximos años en los próximos años. El enfoque de investigación adoptado para el desarrollo de este estudio es una revisión integradora, basada en la aplicación de una metodología de estudio de caso descriptiva, cualitativa y exploratoria. El presente estudio busca evidenciar que China puede no solo integrarse, sino también ser el principal promotor de las condiciones para la plena integración económica y comercial de toda la región y su entorno, dada la prominencia de su papel geopolítico, y porque cuenta con una política de mercado en pleno desarrollo y con un gran potencial de crecimiento. especialmente desde el punto de vista social y económico. El análisis de este conjunto de factores sugiere un escenario favorable para que China ponga en práctica la nueva iniciativa.

Palabras clave: Nueva Ruta de la Seda; China; Eurasia; Mundo Multipolar

1. INTRODUCTION

Since it began to be performed by humanity, according to historical records, trade has decisively influenced the development of societies, the rise and decline of empires, nations, as well as companies, industries, and other production chains that, thanks to international trade, found the conditions to reach another level of development. Even in the period before Christ, China had a moment of relevant protagonism in international trade movements not only at a regional level but also at an intercontinental level, which extended until the middle of the 17th century after Christ. It was from the development of trade routes during the Han Dynasty (207 BC - 220 AD), which later came to be known as the Silk Road, that the Chinese Empire found the path and perhaps the most critical foundation for the periods of prosperity that it began to experience from this period onwards. (IBRACHINA, 2020)

Figure 1 - Map of the Ancient Silk Road

Source: <https://ibrachina.com.br/cultura/conheca-a-historia-da-milenar-rota-da-seda/>

In addition to the Chinese Empire, the Silk Road also played a decisive role in the strengthening and development of other vital empires that emerged prominently throughout history, such as Persia, Mesopotamia, Ancient Egypt, and the Roman Empire, given the volume and added value of the exchanges made possible by the established routes. These were not just commercial exchanges such as silk, which was the main product transported and traded, but also the cultural, technological, religious, and political exchange that this logistical structure promoted (IBRACHINA, 2020). In other words, from the first Chinese experience with establishing trade routes, it is clear that the development of foreign trade has proven essential over time to strengthen the conditions for national, social, and economic development, also individually in countries.

As pointed out by Arrighi (2009), Asia's emergence as one of the most critical regions of the world economy was consolidated in the 21st century (apud KOTZ, 2018), accounting for 29.7% of the global gross domestic product (WORLD BANK DATABASE, 2017). China's well-known and notable economic rise that began in the late 1970s is considered the great driving force behind all economic development in Southeast Asia. The process was driven by reforms and diplomatic openings, with the creation of SEZs (Special Economic Zones) during the period in which the PRC was led by Deng Xiaoping (1978-1989). During the following 30 years, the country achieved an average growth of 10% per year and lifted 500 million people from the poverty line (WORLD BANK, 2013, p. 23).

One of the main projects of Chinese foreign policy today is constructing a new trade route to integrate various consumer markets across various continents, creating more favorable conditions to handle the large volume of goods produced in the PRC. Furthermore, the possibility of expanding China's influence wherever the new routes are established is relevant. The Chinese dream of full development and retaking the lead in international trade motivated the *Beijing government* to create the project. How China intends to deal with other actors in implementing and realizing the same is, at the very least, different from how the current hegemonic power is represented by the United States of America, the European Union, and the Japan Act (BARBOSA et al., 2018).

The New Silk Road is presented in official literature as *Belt and Road Initiative* (BRI), or even *One Belt, One Road* (OBOR), and was officially announced by Chinese President Xi Jinping in 2013, initially involving 65 countries, approximately 62% of the population and 30% of the world's GDP. According to Kotz (2018), "the '*Silk Economic Road*' is designed to be the land component of the program and will pass through Central Asia, the Middle East, Russia, and Europe, basically promoting more effective integration between the countries located in the region known as Eurasia. The land route is complemented by the '*Maritime Silk Road*,' a sea route that will link Chinese ports in Southeast Asia with countries on the African coast, passing through the Indian Ocean, the Suez Canal, and reaching the Mediterranean" (KOTZ, 2018).

As pointed out by Hong (2016), "The initiative is divided into six economic corridors: 1) the New Eurasian Land Bridge; 2) the China-Mongolia-Russia axis; 3) the central China-West Asia axis (passing through the Middle East); 4) the China-Indochina Peninsula axis; 5) the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor axis and, finally, 6) the Bangladesh-China-India and Myanmar Economic Corridor. Strategic reports prepared by the Chinese academy predict that the project implementation process should extend throughout 30 to 40 years" (apud KOTZ, 2018).

In line with the proposal to establish a new Silk Road, China has signed cooperation agreements with countries and organizations within the framework of the "One Belt, One Road" initiative. Investments are expected to be in the order of one trillion dollars.

Figure 2 – Map of the New Silk Road

Source: <https://www.brasildefatorj.com.br/2019/10/25/o-que-ea-nova-rota-da-seda-e-quais-serao-os-impactos-para-a-america-latina>

As can be seen on the map, the “New Silk Road” begins its Chinese section in the city of *Xi’an* but also reaches Beijing to the north and Guandong to the south, heading from there to *Lanzhou* (*Gansu* province), *Urumqi* (*Xinjiang*) and *Khorgas* (*Xinjiang*), already close to Kazakhstan. From there, it enters foreign territories to the southwest, reaching the Middle East, arriving in northern Iran and Central Asia before going through Iraq, Syria, and Turkey. From Istanbul, the new commercial route will head towards Europe through the Bosphorus Strait to Bulgaria, Romania, the Czech Republic, and Germany, where it will arrive at the port of Rotterdam in the Netherlands. Finally, it will reach Venice via the south, where it will integrate with the Maritime Silk Road. (BARBOSA et al., 2018).

China's rapid economic development and increased international prominence in recent decades have reinforced the importance of geopolitics in globalization. China's role in promoting the development of Southeast Asia and historically underdeveloped regions that have been victims of violent colonization processes, such as the African continent itself, is particularly noteworthy. Furthermore, technological investments have placed the PRC at the forefront of development and global trade, standing up to the hegemonic superpowers.

With the development of a "New Silk Road," the People's Republic of China is in line with its prominent history in commercial relations between international actors throughout historical periods. This is supported by all the symbolism of the period in which the "Silk Road" was the main promoter of commercial flow since 200 BC. Thus, this study aims to address China's international insertion with a focus on the land dimension of the New Silk Road.

2. OBJECTIVES

The objective of this study is to present the New Silk Road with emphasis on the land aspect, as well as the relevance that Chinese geopolitics has in the world and in promoting foreign trade. In addition, it correlates international commercial activity with the possibilities of reaching new levels of national socioeconomic development individually in a country.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research approach adopted for this study is an integrative review, employing the descriptive, qualitative, and exploratory case study methodology. Data was collected mainly through the *Scientific Electronic Library Online* (SciELO), covering studies published between 2010 and 2023. This approach sought to capture the most recent trends and developments related to the New Silk Road, with a focus on the initiative's geopolitical and economic implications.

A multi-stage strategy was adopted to analyze and synthesize the information: initially, an exploratory reading was carried out to assess the scope of the texts. Then, a selective reading was performed, filtering the material in search of information aligned with the proposed objectives and theme. The types of documents selected included research articles, government reports, and policy analyses. A detailed summary of the relevant information followed this phase.

Clear inclusion criteria were established based on methodological rigor and significant contribution to the understanding of the subject. Studies that did not meet these criteria were excluded. The results were then interpreted in the context of the research questions, focusing on the correlation between the New Silk Road initiative and China's increasing geopolitical influence.

4. THEORETICAL BASIS

4.1 Geopolitics and Geostrategy of Eurasia

The logistics and strategy of the Eurasia region are of extreme importance in addition to the region's natural and energy resources. Its center is commonly known as the Heartland, a term created by *Mackinder* in 1904 that expresses the broad potential of this area, which extends from Eastern Europe to East Asia.

This large area encompasses the Arctic Circle, the deserts, and the South Asian mountains. It also includes the Baltic Sea, the Black Sea, the Caspian Sea, and the Persian Gulf, waters that are particularly important for commercial strategies. The only accessible naval routes are the Baltic Sea and the Black Sea. The northern part, covered almost entirely by snow and ice, is protected by deserts and mountains, making the territory practically untouchable by naval means. The various straits within the Heartland can be protected by land power (PETERSEN, 2011 apud KOTZ, 2018).

Figure 3 - Demarcation of the Heartland

Source: <https://bonifacio.net.br/qual-a-importancia-do-tratado-do-rcep-para-a-geopolitica-da-china-na-asia/>

To expand knowledge about the Heartland and connect it to the New Silk Road, it is necessary to understand the concept of Geostrategy: association of the geographic factor (the terrain) with a strategic purpose (employment of organized forces) (CORREIA, 2012). Its unofficial definition at IAEM (Institute of Advanced Military Studies) reflects this meaning:

"Study of the constants and variables of space (...) which, when objectified in the construction of evaluation and employment models, or threat of employment, of forms of coercion, projects geographic knowledge into strategic activity.'"

There is also the concept of Geopolitics, which has similarities with Geostrategy. However, the emphasis is on the differences in the two essential elements of analysis: in the models, they serve – power dynamics for geopolitics, assessment, and use of forms of coercion for Geostrategy – and in the objectives, they aim at – a political activity for geopolitics, strategic activity for Geostrategy (CORREIA, 2012). The definitions of each term according to IAEM are:

Geopolitics: Study of the constants and variables of space that, when aimed at constructing models of power dynamics, projects geographical knowledge into development and political activity (CORREIA, 2012).

Geostrategy: Study of the constants and variables of space that, when aimed at constructing evaluation models and employing forms of coercion, projects geographic knowledge into strategic activity (CORREIA, 2012).

According to the data, connecting this important territory to the New Silk Road has currently been one of China's increasingly systematic efforts. This follows the line of thought pointed out by thinkers such as Mackinder (1919; 1944), Spykman (1969), Brzezinski (1997; 2016), and Frankopan (2015), among others (KOTZ, 2018) regarding the geopolitical and strategic importance of Eurasia.

China has been a great military and economic power since the end of the 20th century. Dominating the *Heartland* means that China has a powerful geostrategic position, rivaling Russia itself - the state that holds the position when it comes to

territorial advantages - as it would be an oceanic front with the continental rearward of the pivot region, positioning it for the rise in the medium term to land and sea power simultaneously. The emergence of this amphibious power would completely subvert the balance of power in Eurasia (MELO, 1994).

4.2 Chinese Geostrategy in Eurasia

Chinese geography was decisive in the millennia-long historical process that shaped the structures of Chinese power—with desert territories to the West, and lands of fertile soil located in the northeast, south-central, and east, rulers established their bases in the regions where it was possible to achieve greater prosperity. One of the most prominent human actions during this process was the construction of the Grand Canal connecting the Yellow and *Yangtze Rivers*, which took place between 605 and 611. It was essential to link the productive regions to the desert regions, promoting the exchange of surplus food products and being decisive for the territorial consolidation of the Chinese State, the second largest in the world. (KAPLAN, 2012, p. 117-119 apud KOTZ, 2018).

Cohen (2015) states that thanks to the voluminous Chinese territory, the thinking of ancient Chinese society was based on self-sufficiency and isolation during the period of closure between the 14th and 15th centuries. Still, according to Cohen (2015), cited by Kotz (2018), "For more than three millennia of the history of Chinese civilization, its geopolitical orientation was predominantly continental, in the search for defense and the establishment of tributary ties about the peoples of Central Asia (Huns et al., among others)." During the 20th century, the People's Republic of China focused its geopolitical action on the territorial strip known as *Heartland* (COHEN 2015 apud KOTZ 2018).

"China's ancient history is full of episodes where the country carried out large-scale initiatives that also refer to the magnitude of the New Silk Road, as highlighted by Barbosa (2018), "China has a history of great undertakings. A strong example is the construction of the Great Wall to protect the country from foreign invasions. In this new era, the 'One The Belt and Road' has been prioritized in China's domestic and, especially, foreign policy. It has also attracted divergent opinions worldwide. While some see it as a project that will bring countless benefits to Eurasia and Africa, others believe it is just a way for China to gain more power and influence in these regions. However, regardless of opinions, this megaproject takes shape daily and could greatly change global relations." (BARBOSA et al., 2018)

China wants to be the incredible power of the Eurasian landmass, while the United States is the tremendous transatlantic power. It is possible to say that by proposing the OBOR initiative, the PRC's foreign policy seeks, in addition to establishing conditions for its development, to undermine U.S.U.S. influence in the region by gaining market share and promoting the development of the necessary (and historically neglected) infrastructure to enable the exchange of goods between the countries.

4.3 China's Global Insertion

The ability of the largest country in Asia to establish itself as an essential player in the contemporary world is confirmed by the levels of economic growth that China has shown in recent decades. Former World Bank Senior President Justin Yifu Lin stated that in less than 40 years, China has reached an upper-middle-class income level (LIN, 2015 Apud Barbosa, 2018). This accelerated development of the Chinese economy has enabled the country to build its new influence not only in the Asian region but also on a global level (BARBOSA, 2018).

China has grown in transnational corporations in the automotive, textile, technology, and other sectors, where Chinese brands stand out. In other words, in addition to economic influence, and cultural influence, in the 1970s, we saw China as a country that exported low-quality, low-value-added products; today, we have major Chinese brands such as Huawei, the leader in the Chinese domestic smartphone market since mid-2020 and the first technology company to launch 5G, which will enable the definitive entry of production models into the 21st century, with the internet as the primary tool promoting this new reality.

Therefore, based on the premise that the world economy is unstable, China presents the *One Initiative Belt and Road as an option for economic and commercial* processes to take place in a stable scenario through new land and sea interconnections meeting everyone's desires. Unlike the ancient Silk Road, China has sea routes as a priority. The decrease in the rate of internal growth raises the alarm signal. It intensifies the need to increase competitiveness in developed markets and to seek markets that are still developing, such as Africa and Latin America, to enable the Chinese State to continue developing and meeting the goals established by the five-year plans. (SANG, 2019).

It is essential to highlight the PRC's efforts to promote a proud, assertive, and fair international relations policy. While we see other powers trying to conclude agreements that benefit only themselves, China follows a guideline where mutual benefit should be the main guideline for international negotiations and initiatives. China does not do this out of benevolence or charity: enabling new markets to develop and grow is essential for the success of the new trade routes planned by Beijing.

4.4 The New Silk Road and Its Overseas Capabilities

In addition to its economic objectives, the New Silk Road's perspective for China is to promote diplomatic and cultural rapprochement, mainly with Western nations, which have always been distant from the Chinese reality, whether for geographical reasons or because of agreements with other countries. Furthermore, one of its main guidelines is to impose a methodology to differentiate itself from the current geopolitical model in vogue. In other words, to the detriment of the common wars, aggressions, and the routine promotion of prejudices against certain ethnic groups, the PRC seeks to maintain peace before the international community as an essential requirement for the advancement of the project. (BARBOSA et al., 2018)

Sang (2019) also emphasizes that, despite the doubts surrounding China's ability to make such a significant investment, the world's current sources of financing are so significantly diversified that it will even be possible to make significant investments in the Americas. As can be seen in the analysis by Pires and Paulino (2017),

"Its effects on Latin America will depend on the extent to which this greater productive integration in Eurasia can result in the diversion or creation of trade about other regions of the world. It is important to note that Asia is already Latin America's main partner and that trade between the two regions presents a high degree of complementarity. This greater productive integration at the Eurasian level may make China less dependent on imports of some commodities from more distant regions, which could negatively affect trade with Latin America. It is important to consider, however, that sustainable growth in Asia in the long term will also represent new export opportunities, especially in food." (PIRES; PAULINO, 2017)

China has recently demonstrated its ability to invest overseas. During the opening of the 73rd World Health Assembly, held on May 18, 2020, President Xi Jinping announced investments of around USD 2 billion, the construction of a *hub warehouse* in partnership with the WHO to enable more agile responses to unexpected pandemic events, and a cooperation mechanism between Chinese hospitals and 30 other African hospitals to accelerate the development of the health system on that continent.

Over 370 projects are underway in Asia alone, including optimizing and constructing ports, highways, railways, gas pipelines, oil pipelines, power plants, and transmission lines (PAUTASSO; UNGARETTI, 2020). In addition to expanding the flow of Chinese manufactured goods to foreign markets and enabling the export of excess Chinese industrial capacity, investment in regional physical infrastructure, especially transportation infrastructure, has a solid geopolitical and geostrategic impact beyond the benefits to the domestic economy.

The initiative already has the formal participation of more than 130 countries and dozens of notable regional and international organizations, paving the way for the prospect of realizing an investment of more than 1.3 billion dollars in the coming years. So far, more than 700 billion dollars have been invested, intensifying the process of reorganizing the economic gravitational pole of the Asian continent. China seeks to consolidate the resumption of regional protagonism based on the Sinocentric logic, just like in the times of the ancient Silk Road. (PAUTASSO; UNGARETTI, 2020)

China's economic and technological growth supports its current role as a global power, which China skillfully uses to project itself regionally in Eurasia, displacing once-hegemonic Western interests to the margins. China's vast territorial space borders fourteen countries on land. It has a direct maritime border with three others: Japan, the Philippines, and South Korea (in addition to Taiwan, which is not recognized as an independent state by Beijing). Approximately 2 billion people live in neighboring countries, and another 1.4 billion live in China. In other words, almost half of the world's population. (COHEN, 2015 apud KOTZ, 2018).

The Chinese Communist Party has a vital source of legitimacy in its five-year plans with the population due to the social advances promoted by this policy of goals.

Thus, the New Silk Road was born as an economic project with robust geopolitical interests so that the PRC could maintain the high rates of internal economic development of recent decades and expand its influence in the region, weakening the presence and dependence on the West. China's foreign policy of non-intervention and peacekeeping should continue unless some Western interest creates obstacles to the full implementation of the project. (BEESON & LI, 2016)

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

China's economic and technological growth supports its current role as a global power, which China skillfully uses to project itself regionally in Eurasia, displacing once-hegemonic Western interests to the margins. China's vast territorial space borders fourteen countries on land. It has a direct maritime border with three others: Japan, the Philippines, and South Korea (in addition to Taiwan, which is not recognized as an independent state by Beijing). Approximately 2 billion people live in neighboring countries, and another 1.4 billion live in China. In other words, almost half of the world's population. (COHEN, 2015 apud KOTZ, 2018).

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Table 1 – List of studies

TITLE	METHODOLOGY	AUTHOR	YEAR
New Silk Road and China's Peaceful Rise	Bibliographic Review	BARBOSA, Manually ; et. al.	2018
China's Place in a Regional and World Governance.	Bibliographic Review	BEESON, Mark; LI, Fujian.	2016
China's One Belt, One Road: an overview of the debate	Bibliographic Review	HONG, Zhao.	2016
The New Silk Road: between historical tradition and the geostrategic project for the future	Bibliographic Review	KOTZ, Ricardo Lopez.	2018
The new silk routes and their impacts on the world economy.	Bibliographic Review	PIRES, Marcos C.; PAULINO, Luis A.	2017
China's Geostrategy and the New Silk Road: An analysis of official Chinese documents and their implications for Brazil.	Bibliographic Review	BLOOD, BEIBEI.	2020

Source: Authors' data.

In this study, we sought evidence that China could become fully integrated and be the primary driver of integration, given the relevance of its regional leadership

role in Eurasia, as well as its growing influence at a global level and mainly because it has a market with significant growth potential and is also the target of robust state policies that seek to promote increased industrial production, logistical capacity and purchasing power of the population. As rightly pointed out by SANG:

“This is, therefore, a very ambitious project by China, which presents itself to the world with all the immensity it possesses, emerging as a new superpower, where the image of the recent past as an underdeveloped and polluted country is being transformed into a new image, now of a country that values its economic achievements, the value of its people and its ancient culture. A China of the 21st century.” (SANG, pg. 89, 2020.)

When analyzing the articles shown in the table, it was possible to see that all of them use the methodology under bibliographic review, so more studies and subsequent developments regarding the topic will be necessary to discuss the subject more broadly. However, all of the studies suggest a series of investments, especially in logistics infrastructure, to complete the new initiative.

It is essential to be aware of how China is expanding, being the second-largest economy in the world today and constantly growing. The country has investment projects in the African continent and the Latin portion of the American continent, such as the Nicaragua Canal or the transoceanic railway, which aims to connect the port of Açu in Rio de Janeiro to Peru. In this way, the country intends to connect Eurasia by land - connecting Europe with Asia, and by sea and ocean waters - connecting Asia with Africa. This project interests several countries, such as Russia, which will directly benefit from the trade routes that will cross its territory. It is believed that this project materializes the ambition of the People's Republic of China to become the world's first economy.

The results have given us the prospect that a new Asian bloc could emerge from which the world's largest economy, the United States, would be excluded. An excellent example of this perspective is that in November 2020, the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) was signed and reported as the world's most significant free trade agreement. Therefore, the U.S.U.S. has not spoken openly about the matter but has begun to boycott the works through its companies that sell engineering equipment to China, in addition to promoting destabilization and interference in the region.

China has never been as prominent as it is today. The Asian dragon is currently investing heavily in implementing the New Silk Road, which will leave 63% of the world's population under its direct influence in the economic, political, commercial, infrastructure, and cultural areas.

6. CONCLUSION

It is possible to conclude that the *Belt and Road Initiative*, announced in 2013 by the Chinese government, and its respective developments are excellent examples of how the development of trade relations between different countries is also essential for promoting each country's national development. The People's Republic of China is focusing on this project to avoid stagnation in its social and

economic development and possibly enable the very high levels achieved in recent decades to be raised to new levels.

The project that became popularly known as the "New Silk Road" still conveys a categorical message that only by expanding, integrating, modernizing, and optimizing the available infrastructure will it be possible to promote an economic model that enables intelligent growth and mutually benefits the parties involved. The Chinese effort to invest in logistics infrastructure should be seen as an example by the Brazilian authorities who, in a continental country like Brazil, exempt themselves from diversifying the limited national transportation matrix, thus hindering Brazil's path to becoming a developed nation.

The security challenges of the New Silk Road represent not only a potential obstacle to Eurasian integration but also to the rise of China. Many territories and interests are involved in the Chinese plan, and many of these countries are experiencing crises, wars, and a series of other factors that cause instability. Therefore, the rebirth of Asia, with the recreation of the Sinocentric system as its central axis, just like the new world order in the making, is linked to the degree of tensions and conflicts in the Eurasian region and, above all, to the forms of accommodation between the established power (the United States) and the emerging one (China).

In one way or another, the mere existence of a project of such magnitude is already valid for future reflection and observations regarding its progress or stagnation. However, despite the resistance imposed by adverse interests, the initiative continues to advance, supported by organizations such as the SCO (Shanghai Cooperation Organization), the RCEP mentioned above, BRICS itself (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa), and the dozens of bilateral and multilateral initiatives that China supports throughout the region of interest.

The New Silk Road, inserted in the reality of new technologies emerging in the 21st century, is an unprecedented undertaking that will raise foreign trade operations to a level never before experienced and should serve as a reference for the elaboration of integration and development plans in the most varied regions of the planet.

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